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The Antes: A Model of Functional Continuity in the Borderlands and the Chronology of the Formation of the Slavic Koine (Fourth-Sixth Centuries)

The Persistence of the Name between the Sarmatian-Iranian and Slavic Worlds

Abstract

In this study, the ethnonym ‘Antes’ is analysed as an onomastic category of the Central and Eastern European borderlands and as a case study for models of the Early Slavic koine (4th–6th centuries). Based on the accounts of Jerome (Chronicon, 334), Ammianus Marcellinus, Jordanes (c. 551), Procopius and Menander Protector, it is shown that the Antes functioned in the 6th century as a community closely linked to the Slavic world, whilst the name itself may retain an older, Sarmatian-Iranian semantic layer associated with the frontier, guarding and border control. A comparison of this material with the Indo-Aryan terms *antapāla*, *pāla/pālaka* and *argala* allows us to situate the Antes within the well-attested conceptual field of ‘border–guard–barrier’ and interpret them as a borderland ethnonym rather than a simple ethnic name. This approach is linked to Florin Curta’s concept of a Slavic lingua franca and models of koineisation, which allows us to view the Early Slavic language as a communicative idiom of the Danube-Pontic zone, rather than merely ‘the language of a single tribe from a single Urheimat’, in the absence of a clear “novelty effect” in the descriptions of these communities by 6th-century authors. In the discussion section, a hypothesis of functional continuity is formulated between the Limigantes (Sarmatae servi) known from sources for the year 334 and the Antes of the 6th century, along with an interpretation of lexical and dietary traces (*strava*, *medos*, *millet*) in the Huns’ vicinity (c. 448) as signs of a maturing Slavic borderland koine, supported by the latest biomolecular research on the diet of the early Slavs. A Bayesian heuristic approach and the principle of parsimony suggest that the model of an earlier presence of a Slavic-speaking population in the borderland formations (4th–5th centuries) better integrates the available historical, philological, lexical and archaeobotanical sources than the traditional picture of the ‘sudden’ appearance of the Slavs only around the year 500.

Keywords: Antes, Jordanes, Procopius, borderland ethnonym, Sarmatians, Early Slavic koine, *antapāla*, *pālaka*, *argala*.

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1. Historical and source-based overview of the issue

1.1. Research problem

The ethnonym Antes is one of the most difficult collective names of late antiquity in Central and Eastern Europe. On the one hand, 6th-century sources place the Antes very close to the Sclaveni, and according to Procopius, both communities are even said to speak ‘the same language’. On the other hand, the name itself has long raised suspicions that it may not have been originally Slavic and that it preserves an older layer of nomenclature, which some researchers associate with an Iranian or Sarmatian-Iranian background. The central question is therefore not simply: “Who were the Antes?”, but rather: does the ethnonym ‘Antes’ retain an older, pre-Slavic layer of meaning, even though the community known from 6th-century sources was already operating within a Slavic linguistic and cultural context? This starting point allows us to avoid two oversimplifications: firstly, the automatic identification of the name with a purely Slavic origin; secondly, the equally automatic tracing of it back to a single, unbroken Sarmatian-Iranian lineage.

1.2. Argaragantes and Limigantes: an earlier Late Roman background

The earliest material relevant to the present problem does not yet concern the Antes themselves, but the Argaragantes and Limigantes, attested in the late Roman world along the Danube. In Jerome’s *Chronicon*, under the year 334, we find a laconic but very important sentence: “The Limigantes Sarmatians, having gathered a force, expelled their masters, who are now called the Argaragantes, onto Roman soil.” This testimony is crucial, as it preserves the social relationship between the two names: the Limigantes appear as a subordinate or rebellious group, whilst the Argaragantes appear as the dominant class displaced from their former position. Ammianus Marcellinus provides a much fuller context. In Book XVII of the *Res Gestae*, he describes the world of the late Sarmatians as politically unstable, socially stratified and embroiled in negotiations with the Empire. Of particular importance to our discussion are his phrases describing the Sarmatian petitioners’ paralysis with fear: “*amisso vocis officio prae timore*” and “*cuius ora formido muta claudebat*”. These are not yet etymological data, but they show that the late Sarmatian world along the middle Danube was perceived by Roman authors not only in ethnic terms, but also in terms of status and politics. Here an important methodological point arises: names such as Argaragantes and Limigantes do not function as simple ethnonyms in the modern sense. They are simultaneously names of groups, strata of dependency and political configurations of the borderlands. This observation will also be significant for the interpretation of the name Antes (Jerome, *Chronicon* ad a. 334; Ammianus Marcellinus, *Res Gestae* XVII.12.9-10; Dimitrov 2017).

1.3. Jordanes: the Veneti, the Sclaveni and the Antes

For the Antes themselves, Jordanes remains the starting point. In the *Getica* we read: “*quam, quamvis nunc per diversa nomina et loca effusa, tamen principaliter Sclaveni et Antes nominantur.*” In Mierow’s translation: “Though their names are now dispersed amid various clans and places, yet they are chiefly called Sclaveni and Antes.” The second passage from Jordanes concerns the location of the Antes: “*Antes vero, qui sunt fortissimi ex eis, de Danastro extenduntur usque ad Danaprum, flumina multis inter se discreta spatiis.*” In translation: “The Antes, who are the bravest of these peoples dwelling in the curve of the Sea of Pontus, spread from the Danaster to the Danaper, rivers that are many days’ journey apart.” These two quotations provide three key pieces of information. Firstly, the Antes are a name clearly distinct from the Sclaveni. Secondly, their territory is borderland, stretching between the great rivers of the Pontic region. Thirdly, in the author’s view, this community has a distinctly warlike character. All this fits well with the

understanding of them as a borderland community, rather than merely one of the anonymous barbarian groups. Elsewhere, Jordanes also recounts a tradition concerning Winitharius's war against the Antes and the execution of their leader: “their king, named Boz”, along with his sons and seventy nobles. Regardless of the historical reliability of the details, the very presence of the ruler's name is highly significant. It indicates that the Antes functioned not merely as a geographical label, but as the name of a political community conceived as capable of leadership and organisation (Jordanes, *Getica* 34-35, 119; Mierow 1915; Kardaras 2016, 2018).

1.4. Procopius: the same language, a different name

If Jordanes provides primarily maps and a record of tradition, Procopius offers the most important ethnographic description. In Dewing's translation, this passage reads: “For these peoples are neither Sclaveni nor Antae, but in ancient times they were called by one and the same name, Sporoi, because they lived scattered. They have the same language, and they are not different from one another in appearance or in customs; they have an utterly barbarous tongue.” This testimony is central to the argument. It shows that by the mid-6th century, the ethnonym Antes no longer denoted a community linguistically distinct from the Sclaveni. Rather, it indicates that the Byzantine author retains two names for communities which he perceives as very close, but not entirely identical. The methodological conclusion is straightforward: the etymology of a name and the language of a community at the time of attestation need not be the same phenomenon.

1.5. The absence of a ‘novelty effect’ in the descriptions of the Sclaveni and the Antes

For the proposed model, it is not only what Procopius and Jordanes say about the ancient common name of the Sclaveni and the Antes that is significant, but also what they do not say about them. In the accounts of both authors, there is not a word about the ‘sudden appearance of a new people’ or a ‘new language’ on the historical stage. On the contrary, Procopius emphasises that the Sclaveni and the Antes “speak the same language” and that “in ancient times” they bore “one and the same name, Sporoi”, which suggests to him a process of differentiation of names within an already existing community rather than its sudden emergence. Jordanes writes in a similar vein, stating that the Veneti, Sclaveni and Antes “now” bear different names, though they derive from a single stock: “Although they may now be scattered among various peoples and names, they are nevertheless chiefly called the Slavs and the Antes. [...] All these, having originated from a single stock, have now produced three names, namely the Veneti, the Antes and the Slavs.” This manner of writing stands in marked contrast to the way late antique authors react to genuinely new or shocking ethnic formations. Ammianus Marcellinus, in describing the Huns, emphasises the suddenness of their appearance and the radical strangeness of their customs: “The Huns, a race savage beyond all compare, dwelt at first beyond the Maeotic marshes, on the far side of the Sea of Azov; and since, from their very cradle, there was in them a fierce desire to plunder others' property, they traversed the lands of the Alans [...] and, with increasing boldness, made a sudden incursion into the extensive and fertile districts of Ermenrichus.” In Ammianus, the Huns are a “people savage beyond all measure” who “suddenly” burst into the known world – this is a typical description of a “new people”. Procopius, on the other hand, when speaking of the Hephthalites, very clearly emphasises their distinctiveness from the “ordinary” Huns: “For they are not nomads like the other Hunnic peoples, but have long been settled in a fertile land. Consequently, they have never made any incursion into Roman territory except in conjunction with the Median army. They are the only ones among the Huns who have fair complexions and features that are not unattractive; and they do not lead a savage way of life, but have an orderly society, and observe right and justice in their

dealings with one another and with their neighbours.” The difference between the description of genuinely “new” peoples and the way in which Jordanes and Procopius speak of the Sclaveni and the Antes is summarised in the table below.

Criterion of description	“New” people (Huns, Hephthalites, Avars)	Long-established people (Sclaveni, Antes)
Vocabulary of appearance	Ammianus stresses the sudden irruption of the Huns as a people “savage beyond all measure”, suddenly bursting into the known world and devastating the lands of Ermenrich.	Jordanes and Procopius do not speak of a sudden appearance; rather, they state that these communities are “now” called differently than “in former times”.
Assessment of customs and appearance	Ammianus describes the Huns as radically alien in their customs, living like “beasts”, and as physically repellent. Procopius, in turn, contrasts the Hephthalites with other Huns in order to emphasise their distinctiveness.	Procopius states explicitly that the Sclaveni and the Antes “do not differ from one another in appearance or customs”; the difference concerns the name, not the cultural profile.
Nomadism / settled life	The Hephthalites are singled out as “not nomads like the other Huns” and as “long settled in a fertile land”, which marks them as exceptional within the Hunnic world.	No such contrast is drawn for the Sclaveni and the Antes. Procopius treats them jointly and does not emphasise any radical change in way of life.
Framework of origin / “stock”	Descriptions of the Huns and Avars do not invoke an earlier common name; the emphasis falls on threat and difference.	Jordanes offers the formula “hi omnes ab una stirpe exorti... Veneti, Antes, Sclaveni”, explicitly locating them within a single line of descent.
“Novelty effect” in the narrative	Strong: the Huns and Avars appear as new and formidable forces whose arrival marks a turning point for the imperial frontier.	Weak or absent: the Sclaveni and the Antes are presented as a population already known, once bearing one name and now several, while still speaking the same language.

1.6. Menander and Theophylact: the Antes as a political actor

Later Byzantine sources shift the emphasis from ethnography to politics. Menander Protector, writing in the second half of the 6th century, already speaks of “leaders of the Antes”, and thus not of an anonymous people, but of a community possessing its own leaders and taking action against the Avars and Byzantium. Theophylact Symocatta, writing in the early 7th century, focuses rather on specific Slavic leaders and on broader terms such as *ethnos*, which may suggest a weakening of the earlier distinctiveness of the name Antes. Such a development fits well with the model of a border community: a name can be very distinct as long as it corresponds to a real political and strategic configuration. When this configuration changes, the name may become blurred, even if the population and part of the elite remain in place.¹

¹ Kardaras, “Sclaveni and Antes,” 405-425; Menander Protector; Theophylact Simocatta.

2. The state of etymological research and a philological analysis of the ethnonym ‘Antes’

2.1. Levels of analysis and the state of research

In the study of the ethnonym Antes, it is necessary to distinguish between three levels: (1) the status of the historical community described in the 6th century; (2) the history of the name itself; and (3) the semantic field to which the name may have belonged. Such a distinction helps to avoid the error of automatically equating the group’s contemporary language with the original meaning of its name. In this sense, Procopius provides data on the historical community, rather than directly on the origin of the ethnonym. This distinction is the starting point for all further analysis. In studies of the name Antes, three main lines of interpretation emerge: Slavic, Iranian and a secondary Caucasian one. Whilst the first corresponds well to Procopius’s description of the community, it does not convincingly resolve the problem of the name itself. Kardaras clearly emphasises that, following their formation, the Antes are widely recognised as a Slavic people, but the ethnic origin and etymology of the name remain controversial. For the present analysis, the interpretative line allowing for an Iranian origin of the name Antes is of fundamental importance. Kardaras summarises this school of thought unequivocally: the view of the Iranian origin of the name was promoted by many scholars, including Vernadsky, Werner, Schramm and Bubenok. In this research tradition, the name is often associated with the semantic field of the edge, the border, or the frontier. At the current stage of research, this is not a solution that enjoys absolute consensus. It is, however, a genuine, enduring and methodologically sound line of interpretation. It may therefore be accepted as the basis for further analysis, provided it is not confused with an automatic ethnic claim.²

2.2. From etymology to the function of the borderland

If we accept that one plausible research hypothesis links ‘Antes’ to the concept of a frontier or borderland, then this name ceases to appear as a mere ethnic designation and begins to function as a term for a borderland. This shift in perspective is fundamental. The question is not only which language the name derives from, but also whether it belongs to a broader field of concepts denoting a border zone, its protection and its administration. At this point, Sanskrit and, more broadly, Indo-Iranian material becomes indispensable, as it provides a well-attested lexical complex with precisely this semantics.³

3. The semantic model of the borderland: anta, antapala, pala/palaka, argala

3.1. Antapala and the semantic field of the borderland

The strongest point of comparison is the Sanskrit term antapala. In the epigraphic glossary, this term is defined as “frontier-guard” and, according to some interpretations, “officer in charge of the boundaries”; its use is also noted in the Arthashastra, the Kamandakiya-nitisara and the Malavikagnimitra. The Practical Sanskrit-English Dictionary defines antapala as “a frontier-guard, guarding the frontiers”, Benfey as “guardian of the frontiers”, Cappeller as “frontier-guard”, and Monier-Williams as the “guardian of the frontiers”. antapala: “frontier-guard”; “guardian of the boundaries”; “officer in charge of the boundaries.” This term shows that in the Indo-Aryan world there exists a well-attested formation combining precisely those two elements which are most important for the model: • anta = limit, boundary, edge, • pala = guard, defender, one who keeps

² Curta, *The Making of the Slavs*; Kardaras, “Sclaveni and Antes.”

³ Sircar, *Indian Epigraphical Glossary*; Monier-Williams, s.vv. antapala, palaka, argala.

watch. This does not yet mean that Antes should be derived from antapala. It does, however, show that the semantic combination of “boundary” and “guard” is a genuine linguistic category attested in Sanskrit sources, rather than a later interpretative construct. The second component of the model is the Sanskrit pala / palaka. In lexicographical tradition, palaka means “protector, guardian, keeper”, but also “ruler, prince, sovereign”. Dictionary compilations also include meanings such as “horse-keeper” and, secondarily, “horse”, which demonstrates the versatility of this lexeme in both administrative and political language, as well as in practical usage. palaka: “protector, guardian, keeper”; also “ruler, prince, sovereign.” Three aspects of this semantics are significant for the proposed model. Firstly, a palaka is someone who protects. Secondly, the same word can denote a ruler, which demonstrates the closeness of the fields of protection and sovereignty. Thirdly, this lexeme is productive both onomastically and lexically. In lexicographical materials and narrative compendia, Palaka also appears as the proper name of various rulers and literary heroes, but here this layer is of secondary importance: it confirms the vitality of the lexeme, not the etymology of Antes. The third important element is argala. In Sanskrit dictionaries, it means ‘bolt, bar, crossbar, latch’, and more broadly: an obstacle, a bolt or an element blocking a passage. It is an important component of the semantic field of the borderland, as it shows that a border is not merely the end of a space, but also a place where it is closed off, blocked and controlled. argala: “bolt, bar, crossbar, latch”; hence also an obstacle or hindrance. The role of argala in this model is auxiliary. This lexeme does not provide a direct etymology for Antes, nor does it resolve names of the Argaragantes type. However, it reinforces a broader semantic reconstruction: boundary / border — guard / protection — bolt / control of entry.⁴

3.2. Minimal semantic model

Based on the material discussed above, a minimal semantic model of the borderland can be reconstructed, consisting of three axes:

1. topographical axis: anta = boundary, edge, border zone;⁵
2. protective and political axis: pala / palaka = guard, guardian, ruler;⁶
3. axis of passage control: argala = bolt, latch, entrance lock;⁷

In this framework, antapala emerges as a central term, as it merges the first and second axes into a single conceptual formation. This is precisely what makes it the strongest semantic parallel for the analysis of the name Antes.⁸

4. The Antes in the borderland model: a comparative analysis of Roman, Byzantine and steppe sources

4.1. The three main sources on the Antes: Jordanes, Procopius and Menander

Jordanes presents the Antes as a community situated between the Dniester and the Dnieper, a valiant people with their own political elite. Procopius, on the other hand, describes them as a community speaking the same language as the Sclaveni. Only when taken together do these sources

⁴ Sircar, *Indian Epigraphical Glossary*; Monier-Williams, s.vv. antapala, palaka, argala; Benfey, s.v. antapala; Cappeller, s.v. antapala.

⁵ Kardaras, “Sclaveni and Antes,” 408-410.

⁶ Monier-Williams, s.v. palaka.

⁷ Monier-Williams, s.v. argala.

⁸ Monier-Williams, s.v. antapala; Sircar, *Indian Epigraphical Glossary*.

provide a complete picture: the Antes are both a distinct political name and part of the Slavic linguistic landscape. This source configuration fits well within the borderland model. The name need not be identical to the community's current language; it may retain an older layer, provided it still corresponds to a real political and regional function. The third of the fundamental testimonies comes from Menander Protector, who, in speaking of the "leaders of the Antes", shifts the analysis from the level of ethnography to that of politics. Here, the Antes appear no longer as an anonymous people, but as a leading community, entangled in relations with the Avars and Byzantium. This fits well with the borderland model: such communities may be important primarily in strategic terms, not necessarily as classical 'tribes' in the ethnographic sense.⁹

4.2. The Argaragantes and Limigantes as a typological analogy

The names Argaragantes and Limigantes clearly demonstrate that late antiquity was familiar with communities whose names were simultaneously social, political and military in nature. Jerome and Ammianus provide the context here for the world along the Danube, where a group's name could signify more than just ethnic origin. However, it cannot be claimed that the Argaragantes are a direct key to the Antes. Rather, they are a typological analogy: they show that the names of borderland groups could denote communities of dependency, domination and military function. A similar structural configuration is clearly evident in 6th–8th-century Avar-Slavic relations. Fredegar's Chronicle presents a picture of the Avars as the overlords of the Slavs and of a Slavic rebellion associated with the figure of Samon, which led to the weakening of Avar authority in part of the region. For a long time, archaeology treated the richly furnished cemeteries of Pannonia and Lower Austria as uniformly "Avar", as they shared a common repertoire of material cultural elements (weapons, belts, horse burials, and a steppe style). It was only the most recent aDNA analyses of two large 7th–8th-century cemeteries south of Vienna (Mödling and Leobersdorf) that revealed the existence of a distinct genetic barrier: one community had an East Eurasian and steppe profile, whilst the other was predominantly European, with virtually identical burial customs, and this difference was maintained over several generations. This case provides a strong typological argument against simple identifications of the 'political name = ethnos = language' type. For it shows that within a single political and cultural order ("the Avars"), populations of different origins and likely different languages can coexist, and a shift in the dominance structure — as in the case of the Slavic revolt — need not disrupt population continuity. Such a model corresponds well with the present proposal to interpret the Argaragants and Limigants as dominant and subordinate strata within a single borderland system, and with the hypothesis that the Antes represent a later, Slavic-speaking phase of this formation, whilst retaining the older, Sarmatian-Iranian layer of names.¹⁰

4.3. Palakos as a steppe parallel

Palakos, the late Scythian king of Crimea, son of Scilurus and — according to Strabo's account — an ally of the Roxolani under Tasius in the wars against Mithridates VI, should be treated in a similar manner. Strabo (Geogr. 7.3.17) writes explicitly: "Now the Roxolani, under the leadership of Tasius, waged war even against the generals of Mithridates Eupator; they came to assist Palacus, the son of Scilurus, as his allies", after which he adds that the allied army of some fifty thousand men failed to withstand the six thousand men of Diophantus. This episode is significant not only historically. It demonstrates that the Crimean-Pontic region of late Scythia remained a space of

⁹ Jordanes, *Getica* 34-35; Procopius, *History of the Wars* VII.14.22-30; Menander Protector; Curta, *The Making of the Slavs*; Kardaras, "Slaveni and Antes."

¹⁰ Jerome, *Chronicon* ad a. 334; Ammianus Marcellinus, *Res Gestae* XVII.12; Dimitrov, "The Ancient Sarmatians"; Fredegar; Wang et al.,

cooperation between Scythian and Sarmatian elites of Iranian origin, and thus a real environment for onomastics associated with power, protection and war. The name Palakos itself does not have a single canonical etymology accepted in the literature, but it can be convincingly placed within the same broad Indo-Iranian field represented by the Sanskrit pālaka. Classical Sanskrit lexicography attributes to this lexeme the meanings “guard, protector”, “protector; guardian; ruler; prince” and “king”, and thus precisely that set of functions which I associate with the borderlands, protection and authority. Against this backdrop, pālaka also functions as a proper name: the narrative tradition identifies Pāla and Gopāla as the sons of Caṇḍamahāsenā in the Kathāsaritsāgarā, whilst tantric sources attest the secondary meaning of pālaka as “shield”; in the Kāmasiddhistuti we read: “She is resplendent like a thunderbolt, beautiful like fresh coral, and has a bow, arrows, a snare, a hook, a shield (pālaka), and a mātuluṅga fruit attached to her six arms.” This comparison allows us to see in Palakos a genuine Scythian-Pontic example of a ruler's name meaning “guardian/defender”, firmly rooted in the family of meanings protection – authority – shield – guard. It is also worth noting the Persian-Iranian technical material, which reinforces the military context of this field. In the entry FALĀKAN, the Encyclopaedia Iranica defines falākan as “a sling” and traces the term back, probably, to the Avestan fradaxšānā-, adding that “in eastern Persia the variant palakmān/palakmo(n) are employed”. This does not constitute a direct etymology of Palakos, but it shows that similar consonant clusters p-l-k / f-l-k remain in use in technical military vocabulary relating to stone-throwing and ranged weapons. Palakos therefore does not serve here as a decisive argument for the etymology of Antes, but as an important onomastic parallel: the actual name of a ruler from the same vast Black Sea-Sarmatian region, which fits well into the “border – guard – bolt” model, albeit without the same evidential weight as antapāla.¹¹

5. An attempt at philological synthesis: from ethnonym to a model of long-term continuity

5.1. From ethnos to border community

The most defensible conclusion from the material so far is as follows: Antes should be understood not as a simple ethnonym, but as the name of a border community which may have retained an older, Sarmatian-Iranian semantic layer, even though by the 6th century it was already functioning within a Slavic linguistic horizon. This interpretation explains three facts at once: the distinctiveness of the name in Jordanes, the linguistic community in Procopius, and the political nature of the community in Menander. It also allows for a better understanding of the subsequent blurring of the name as the very configuration of the borderland changes. The ethnonym Antes can therefore be treated as a case of a long-lasting political-border name. In such a model, the name is more enduring than the community's language, but less enduring than the geography of the borderland itself: it may be adopted by a new configuration of elites and population, provided it continues to correspond to the function of the zone it denotes. This is not, of course, proof of a single genealogical line from the Sarmatian world to the Slavic communities. It is, however, a strong interpretative proposal consistent with the source, philological and semantic material.¹²

5.2. Limits and application of the model

¹¹ Strabo, Geography 7.3.17; Ivantchik, “The Scythian Kingdom in the Crimea”; Monier-Williams, s.v. palaka; Mohebbi, “FALĀKHAN”; Shahbazi, “ARMY i. Pre-Islamic Iran.”

¹² Curta, The Making of the Slavs; Kardaras, “Sclaveni and Antes.”

This model does not prove that the Antes were simply “Sarmatians”, nor that every similar steppe name can automatically be subsumed under it. Nor does it settle the etymology of the Argaragants or the Palakos. Its strength lies elsewhere: in demonstrating that the name Antes can be situated within a well-attested semantic field of the borderlands and that such a model is consistent with the profile of a community known from late antique sources. In this sense, the Antes are a particularly valuable case study. Not because they provide a simple answer to the question of the ethnogenesis of the Slavs, but because they demonstrate how a political or regional name can retain an older layer of meaning and function within a new linguistic community. It is precisely this that makes them good material for studying the hybridisation of nomenclature and borderland politics. Against this backdrop, the Argaragantes, Limigantes and Palakos remain an important source of supplementary information. They demonstrate that in late antiquity and the steppe world, there were names for communities, elites and rulers whose meaning was not purely ethnic, but was linked to functions of protection, dependency, authority or border location. However, they are not sufficient to resolve the issue of the Antes on their own. This study therefore remains deliberately secondary to the core of the source-philological analysis based on Jordanes, Procopius and Sanskrit material.¹³

5.3. Conclusion and transition to the koine

The safest conclusion of Chapter 5 is as follows: the ethnonym Antes can be interpreted as the name of a borderland that survived a change of language and a partial change of elites, as it retained its political and regional significance as a designation for a border zone community. Such a model is consistent with both the historical material and the reconstruction of the semantic field of *anta* – *pala/palaka* – *argala*. A neolinguistic perspective, particularly Matteo Bartoli’s theory of the periphery, allows us to frame this issue more precisely. In Bartoli’s classical framework, lateral, peripheral areas that are less integrated into centres of innovation tend to retain archaic features, whilst central areas undergo change and reorganisation more rapidly. With regard to the material discussed here, this means that what appears to be a peripheral or relic element in one system may retain the status of a central carrier of an older semantic field in another. Consequently, the archaic connection between the concepts of the border, the guard and the control of passage may persist on the linguistic periphery for longer than in centres of later political and cultural centralisation. This perspective fits well with the model of the Antes as a borderland community. If we assume that by the 6th century the Antes were already operating within the Slavic linguistic horizon—as suggested by Procopius’s account of the ‘same language’ of the Sclaveni and the Antes—while simultaneously retaining an ethnonym rooted in the older Indo-Iranian semantic field of ‘frontier’, ‘boundary’ and ‘guard’, reconstructed on the basis of lexemes such as *antapāla*, this case can be interpreted as a local study of the hybridisation of the lexical repertoire and linguistic practice in the contact zone between the steppe and the Baltic-Slavic world. From this perspective, the difficulty in determining which elements of the ‘border–guard–border control’ field are inherited relics, which are ancient borrowings, and which are later innovations, is not a weakness of the model, but a natural consequence of it. In conditions of prolonged contact and the multi-layered overlapping of centres and peripheries, individual lexemes may become archaic in some areas, disappear in others, and at the same time be reborn as new onomastic or political formations on the same semantic substrate. Therefore, this work does not aim to break each instance down artificially into the opposition of “inherited” versus “borrowed”, but instead focuses on reconstructing the conceptual field itself,

¹³ Curta, *The Making of the Slavs*; Curta, “The Slavic Lingua Franca”; Kardaras, “Sclaveni and Antes.”

within which the border, the guard and the control of passage remain structurally linked. Such an interpretation aligns well with a strand of research that views the Early Slavic language not as a simple ‘language of a single tribe from a single *Urheimat*’, but as a koine developed within a broad zone of political and military contact along the Danube-Pontic arc. Florin Curta, speaking of the ‘Slavic *lingua franca*’, emphasises that in the 6th–7th centuries the Slavic language served as a supra-tribal communicative idiom within the political structures of this zone, rather than merely the idiom of a single, strictly ethnically defined community. In his view, the history of the Sclaveni and the Antes as historical categories begins only around the year 500, which corresponds well with the ‘suddenness’ of the Antes’ appearance in the sources of Jordanes and Procopius and the later role of this community in relations with the Avars. Against this background, the Antes can be treated as one specific configuration of the borderland, in which earlier, probably Sarmatian-Iranian terminology and conceptual fields (“border”, “guard”, “bolt”) are adopted and incorporated into the developing Slavic koine. On the one hand, the ethnonym Antes fits into the Indo-Iranian field of *anta* – *pāla/pālaka* – *argala*, associated with the frontier, protection and control of passage; on the other hand, Procopius unambiguously situates this community within the Slavic “barbarian speech”. The case of the Antes thus serves as an example in which the “political language of the borderland” (border names and categories of potentially Iranian origin) and the “language of communication” (Slavic koine) coexisted within a single historical formation. The case of the Antes does not serve here as evidence for a complete, contact-based reconstruction of the origins of Proto-Slavic. It can, however, be treated as an empirical example of how steppe, Baltic and Slavic languages jointly create a regional borderland koine: the semantics of the frontier and the guard derive from the Iranian repertoire; the communicative practices of the forest-steppe population stem from the local Baltic- Slavic substrate; and the function of a supra-tribal idiom within the larger Avar and Byzantine structures arises from the political configuration of the 6th century. In this sense, the Antes become an important case study for models that view the Slavic language of the early Middle Ages as the koine of the Danube-Pontic zone, rather than merely a simple continuation of a single, ethnically homogeneous idiom.¹⁴

5.4. Names of the ancient community: Sporoi, Veneti, Spali

The accounts of Procopius and Jordanes from the mid-6th century provide insight into how early Byzantine authors understood the origins of the names of the communities we now associate with the Slavs. Procopius, describing the Sclaveni and the Antes, states that ‘in ancient times’ they were all known by a single name, the Sporoi, which he explains by the Greek *sporadēn* (‘scattered’), as they were said to have lived ‘sparsely, scattered like scattered grain’. In H. B. Dewing’s translation, this passage reads: “For these peoples were not originally designated as Sclaveni and Antes, but in ancient times were all known by one and the same name, the Sporoi, because they lived scattered (*sporadēn*), spoke the same language, and did not differ from one another in appearance or customs.” Procopius thus explicitly states that the Sclaveni and the Antes “have the same language” and do not differ in appearance or customs. Jordanes, on the other hand, writing almost simultaneously in the *Getica*, speaks of the Veneti as a people who derive “from one stirps” – from a single stock – and whose names “now” are divided primarily into the Sclaveni and the Antes: “Although they are now scattered among various peoples and bear different names, they are chiefly known as the Slavs and the Antes. [...] All of them originating from a single stock, they have now given rise to three names, namely the Veneti, the Antes and the Slavs.” Both authors thus

¹⁴ Bartoli, *Introduzione alla neolinguistica*; Urban, “Mountain Linguistics”; Curta, “The Slavic *Lingua Franca*”; Curta, *Slavs in the Making*; Lindstedt and Salmela.

present the same pattern: an ancient collective name (Sporoi / Veneti) and a later differentiation into the Sclaveni and the Antes whilst maintaining a single linguistic and cultural community. In other words, Procopius and Jordanes do not describe the sudden ‘appearance’ of many different peoples, but rather the differentiation of political names within a community which they perceive as unified in terms of language and customs. The way in which Procopius explains the name Sporoi is a classic example of folk etymology: a term that sounds foreign is ‘domesticated’ through the Greek lexeme *sporadēn*, without the need to reflect the actual origin of the ethnonym. Later literature has proposed a range of further explanations – from identifying Sporoi with the Slavic ‘*sporo*’ (‘many’), through attempts to see in it a distorted form of ‘Serbs’, to linking Sporoi with the Spalans. At the present stage of research, however, all these proposals remain hypotheses with very uneven evidential weight. A safer conclusion is that as early as the 6th century, there existed in Byzantium and in the Gothic world a conscious discourse regarding an ancient, shared name for a people whom these authors know as the Sclaveni and the Antes – with a clear emphasis on linguistic unity. Against this background, one might cautiously consider the place of other names from the same region, such as Spali / Spalaei / Palaei. Classical sources situate the Spali in the Sarmatian region around the Don, and some scholars regard them as one of the groups associated with the wider Iranian-steppe world. The root *sp-l / p-l* suggests a possible connection with the Indo-Iranian family of forms *pala / palaka* ‘guardian, defender, ruler’, well attested in Sanskrit and more broadly in Indo-Iranian material. The same semantic family also includes *Palakos*, the Scythian-Pontic king known from Strabo’s account, whose name can be typologically linked to the field of protection and sovereignty. This does not mean that Spali can be directly derived from *pala* ‘guard’: the source material does not allow for the reconstruction of a regular phonetic sequence or a specific self-designation formula in the language of this group. It does, however, allow us to identify a functional field — names with the root *p-l* appear in contexts of borderlands, guard duty and military authority, which fits the model in which Iranian border terminology (*anta – pala – argala*) co-creates the political and military language of the Danube-Pontic zone. As part of a typological exercise, one can imagine a scenario in which borderland warriors, when asked in some common idiom (koine) ‘who are you?’, respond with a formula signifying ‘[border] guards’, which is captured and transformed into an ethnonym by Greek- or Latin-speaking authors. The mechanisms of ‘names from conversation’ are well known from other contexts of intercultural contact; here, however, they serve merely as an illustration of how a borderland koine can generate names in interaction with foreign literary centres, rather than as a basis for constructing a fully-fledged historical- linguistic etymology. Such scenarios remain deliberately marked as folk etymology, serving solely to explain the mechanism, rather than to reconstruct a specific dialogue or a specific form. Added to this are echoes of the Iranian war and border repertoire preserved in East Slavic folklore. In Rus’ *bylinas*, the figure of the *polanica/palenica* (*polenica, palenica*) appears — a female warrior on horseback whose main occupation is ‘*polakowanie*’, that is, setting out into the ‘open field’ (an epic figure of the steppe) to seek fame in battle against worthy opponents. Some scholars derive the name *polanica* from the root *pal-*, whilst more recent popular attempts tend to link it to *pole*, which may be a secondary folk etymology based on a superficial similarity of forms. Proposals linking *polanica* to the Iranian *pahlavān* ‘hero, champion’ fit into the same broader picture: Iranian names and titles of steppe warriors permeate Slavic epic memory and are reinterpreted within the local lexical system. Regardless of the ultimate etymology, the fact that *polanice* function as female warriors ‘going out into the open field’ fits well with the military idiom of the open field in the Slavic tradition and with the Iranian-Sarmatian context of the borderlands. In this light, the ethnonym *Polans* need not be understood solely as a neutral term for ‘people of the fields’ in an agricultural sense. A formal

derivation from the Proto-Slavic **polje* ‘field, open space’ remains the most economical linguistic solution, but does not settle whether the original naming impulse was purely topographical or whether it was linked to the military idiom of ‘going out into the field’ and fighting in open spaces, well attested in military practice and Slavic folklore. Similarly to the case of the ethnonym *Slověne* itself, where the dispute between the interpretation ‘from the word’ (‘those who speak [intelligibly]’) and the tradition linking the name to ‘fame’ shows that the relationship between a name and a single, simple ‘keyword’ can be deceptive; similarly, with the Polans, caution is advised against overly unambiguous reinterpretations. In this context, both written sources (Procopius, Jordanes) and the epic tradition (Polanica) present a convergent picture: a single, relatively homogeneous linguistic community, situated in a borderland where Iranian nomenclature and military terminology intermingle with Slavic communicative practice. The model of a Slavic koine emerging in the 4th–6th centuries provides a good explanation for this arrangement as the result of long-term contact, in which old names (Veneti, Sporoi, possibly Spali) and new ethnonyms (Sclaveni, Antes, later Polans) reflect different levels of political and cultural articulation within a single, evolving borderland community.¹⁵

5.5. Lexical traces of the Slavic koine in the 5th century (*strava*, *medos*, *millet*)

I assume that some of the terms attested in the Huns’ sphere of influence in the mid-5th century should be interpreted directly as Slavic, or at least as clearly Slavic-influenced elements of the contact language of that region. This applies primarily to the forms *strava* and *medos/medas*, recorded in the tradition concerning Attila’s state. The current state of research allows for various explanations of these lexemes — Germanic, Iranian or, more broadly, Indo-European — yet Otto J. Maenchen-Helfen already concluded that in the case of *strava*, the most likely explanation is the mediation of a Slavic informant, rather than an authentic Hunnic word. It is therefore not a matter of a coincidental resemblance to Slavic vocabulary, but of a genuine trace of Slavic communicative idiom in the 5th-century milieu. Priscus states: "In the villages we were provided with food—millet instead of corn, and mead, as the natives call it, instead of wine. The attendants who accompanied us received millet and a barley drink called *kam* by the barbarians." This is how the English translation renders a passage from Priscus’s account of his journey to Attila. In philological tradition, the focus is precisely on the forms *medos* and *kamos/kam*, long debated as words belonging to the contact language of the Hunnic state. Maenchen-Helfen summarised this material succinctly: “Medos, too, is Indo-European, either Germanic or Illyrian”, whilst he considered *kamos* to be also Indo-European and older in the Pannonian region than the time of Attila. I assume, however, that in the context of its co-occurrence with *strava* and with the ritual and table-related vocabulary of the steppe-Slavic world, *medos/medas* is best understood as a word already functioning in the Slavic-influenced koine of the borderlands, even if its earlier history remains more complex. "When the Huns had mourned him [Attila] with such lamentations, a *strava*, as they call it, was celebrated over his tomb with great revelling." This statement by Jordanes, referring to Attila’s funeral, is of fundamental importance in this model. Maenchen-Helfen devoted a separate analysis to it and, after rejecting the popular Gothic etymologies, stated: “One of Priscus’ or Jordanes’ informants seems to have been a Slav. Knowing neither Hunnic nor Slavic, Priscus or Jordanes could have taken *strava* for a Hunnic word.” This is one of the strongest arguments in the literature for interpreting *strava* as a Slavic word, or at least one transmitted through Slavic mediation. I accept this line of interpretation as more convincing than solutions which dissolve the

¹⁵ Curta, “The Slavic Lingua Franca”; Curta, *Slavs in the Making*; Lindstedt and Salmela; Encyclopaedia Iranica, “Slavic-Iranian Contacts.”

term into a neutral Indo-European background without taking the source context into account. Millet provides an even stronger context. In Priscus's account, it appears as a staple food in the Hunnic zone, and the latest biomolecular and isotopic studies from Bohemia and Moravia have shown that it is precisely this strong reliance on millet processing that constitutes one of the most distinctive markers of early Slavic populations in Central Europe. Jiří Macháček and his co-authors write explicitly in their 2025 article about a "strong reliance on millet processing by Slavic groups", and a research press release from Masaryk University summarises the findings even more bluntly: the earliest Slavic populations in Central Europe differed from the Germanic peoples in having a diet based to a greater extent on milk, millet and honey. So if, in Attila's realm in the mid-5th century, we find *medos*, *strava* and millet all present as elements of daily life and ritual, this picture fits very well with the presence of an already established Slavic contact idiom within the Hunno-Sarmatian milieu. In light of the principle of economy, the presence of these words at Attila's court and in his entourage should not be treated as a collection of random borrowings. Pospieszny et al.'s study on prehistoric Kuyavia shows that communities occupying the same broad regional ecumene could be sharply distinguished by diet.¹⁶ In the Middle Bronze Age, individuals associated with Tumulus Culture contexts display clear C4 signatures consistent with millet consumption, whereas contemporaneous Trzciniec individuals and earlier populations do not. The authors explicitly distinguish between "millet-eaters" and "non-millet-eaters", and interpret the pattern as evidence for different dietary and subsistence practices rather than as a simple reflection of material culture. Chronologically, this Kuyavian material is much earlier than the Antes and cannot be used as direct evidence for Slavic ethnicity. Its relevance is methodological: it demonstrates that millet consumption may function as a measurable marker of social, economic and cultural differentiation within the same or neighbouring ecological zone. When combined with the early medieval evidence from Bohemia and Moravia, where millet processing is strongly associated with Slavic groups, millet becomes part of a wider diagnostic package linking diet, mobility, table vocabulary and the formation of a frontier koine. It is simpler and, in my view, more accurate to regard this cluster of terms and dietary markers as traces of a Slavic borderland koine, which by the 5th century was already sufficiently established to permeate the language of rituals, the table and everyday life. Viewed in this light, the sequence of sources forms a coherent whole: the 4th century presents the Limigantes as a dependent layer of the borderland world; the 5th century brings *strava*, *medos* and millet in the Huns' surroundings; and the 6th century introduces the Antes, of whom Procopius states that they speak the same language as the Sclaveni. This is not conclusive proof, but the chain of circumstantial evidence is strong enough to allow the beginning of the process of Slavic koineisation to be pushed back to centuries earlier than the moment of the first full visibility of the Slavs in Byzantine sources.¹⁷

6. Final conclusions and the place of the author's hypothesis

6.1. Findings from sources, philology and modelling

At the source level, the material allows us to state with a high degree of certainty that the Antes were, in the 6th century, a documented community of the Pontic-Carpathian borderland, nominally distinct from the Sclaveni, but at the same time linguistically and culturally close to them. Jordanes

¹⁶ Pospieszny, Łukasz, Jamie Lewis, Isabel L. Wiltshire, Lucy Cramp, Julia Giblin, Marta Krenz-Niedbala, Sylwia Łukasik, et al. 2026. "Isotopic Insights into Long-Term Socio-Economic Transformations in Prehistoric Kuyavia, Poland." *Royal Society Open Science* 13: 250968. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.250968>.

¹⁷ Priscus, fr. 8; Jordanes, *Getica* 258; Maenchen-Helfen, *The World of the Huns*, 424-426; Machacek et al.; Curta, "The Slavic Lingua Franca"; Lindstedt and Salmela.

provides their location and a record of their political tradition, Procopius — a description of their linguistic and cultural affinity with the Sclaveni, and Menander — a portrayal of the Antes as a political entity operating in relations with Byzantium and the Avars. These accounts do not suggest that the Antes were simply an Iranian people; rather, it is clear that a name and a historical community need not share the same origin or the same date. From a philological perspective, the key finding is that the name Antes can be meaningfully situated within the well-attested Indo-Iranian semantic field of the borderlands. The most fully attested parallel remains the Sanskrit *antapāla*, accompanied by *pāla/pālaka* and, to a lesser extent, *argalā*; their shared semantics allow us to reconstruct the model ‘frontier / border – guard / protection – control of passage’. This model does not determine the ethnic origin of the Antes, but it shows that the name itself fits well within the lexical repertoire of terms denoting a border zone, its protection, and the closing or ‘barring’ of passages. By combining source and philological material, we arrive at a coherent model in which Antes is best interpreted as a borderland ethnonym, rather than a simple name for a ‘people’ in a biological or linguistic sense. In this interpretation, the name denotes a community operating on the frontier between the steppe and settled worlds, in a strategic, military and political zone, which by the 6th century was already using a Slavic communicative idiom, but may have retained an older, Sarmatian-Iranian semantic layer associated with the border, guarding and control of the crossing. This conclusion is of a model nature: it does not prove a single genealogical line from the Sarmatians to the Slavs, but proposes an interpretation consistent with source, philological and semantic data, as well as with the concept of an early Slavic borderland koine.¹⁸

6.2. The scope of the hypothesis and the significance of the study

A scientifically sound conclusion is as follows: the Antes are a community of the Slavic-speaking borderlands, and the name ‘Antes’ itself may retain an older, probably Sarmatian-Iranian semantic layer associated with the frontier, a guard and a border function. The author’s hypothesis may go a step further and suggest that this ethnonym was a long-standing political and border-related name, adopted by a community which by the 6th century was already established within the Slavic world. Such a model does not contradict the sources, but must be clearly designated as an interpretative hypothesis rather than a definitive conclusion. The contribution of this work lies not in a definitive resolution of a single ethnonym, but in demonstrating that collective names of late antiquity can be studied simultaneously from historical, philological and semantic perspectives. As a result, the Antes cease to be merely an ethnic problem and become evidence of the long-lasting nature of the political language of the borderlands.¹⁹

6.3. The hypothesis of an earlier attestation of the Slavs (Limigantes – Antes)

Against the backdrop of the model of the Antes as a borderland community outlined above, I would like to formulate a working hypothesis which goes beyond the minimum findings of this study, but follows logically from the data collected. This concerns a possible functional continuity between the names Limigantes (4th century) and Antes (6th century), and consequently a shift downwards in the chronology of the participation of the Slavic-speaking population in the borderland structures. As shown in Chapter 1.2, the accounts of Jerome and Ammianus Marcellinus present the Limigantes as a dependent class (*Sarmatae servi*), rebelling against their ‘masters’, the Argaragantes, and functioning in the border zone along the middle Danube. This name does not function as a classical ethnonym, but rather as a status-political designation associated with a

¹⁸ Procopius, *History of the Wars* VII.14.22-30; Jordanes, *Getica* 34-35; Menander Protector; Kardaras, “Sclaveni and Antes.”

¹⁹ Curta, *The Making of the Slavs*; Kardaras, “Sclaveni and Antes.”

specific configuration of the borderland. The etymology of *Limigantes* remains uncertain; attempts have been made in the literature to link it to the Latin *limes* and the terminology *limitanei*, but these are rightly treated with caution. This discussion should not be reduced to a purely formal etymology. The possible association of *Limigantes* with Latin *limes* and the terminology of the *limitanei* is relevant precisely because the group is attested in a Roman frontier context. The form should not be mechanically analysed as *limes* + *Antes*, since the medial *-g-* and the parallel form *Argaragantes* indicate that *-gantes* belongs to the transmitted group-name pattern itself. Yet this does not deprive the name of its frontier value. It may rather suggest a Roman or Romanised functional exonym: *limi-/limig-* denoting the borderland function, and *-gantes / -antes* preserving a group-name or ethno-political component. In this sense, *Limigantes* would not mean “the Antes of the limes” in a strict linguistic sense, but rather “a frontier-associated group”, possibly including populations later visible under the elevated political name *Antes*. For the present proposal, it is more important that the *Limigantes* describe a stratum of dependent and borderland populations, potentially multi-ethnic, rather than a homogeneous ‘people’ in the modern sense. I propose viewing the *Limigantes* as an earlier borderland formation, in which groups speaking dialects close to the later Slavic language may already have participated, whilst the *Antes* represent a later, ‘elevated’ ethnonym of the same zone, functioning under the dominance of the Slavic koine. A comparison of dates (the *Limigant* revolt around 334, the appearance of the *Antes* in Jordanes and Procopius in the mid-6th century) suggests that the ‘sudden’ appearance of the Slavs in the sources around the year 500 may be the result of a change in the descriptive category, rather than the beginning of the actual presence of a Slavic-speaking population in the borderland systems. From this perspective, the Slavic language and earlier Indo-Iranian dialects are not radically alien to one another, but sufficiently close that prolonged coexistence within structures of dependency — such as those described by the names *Limigantes* and *Sarmatae servi* — favoured the emergence and rapid spread of a Slavic koine in the 6th century. If we assume that the linguistic substrate in the region between the Danube borderlands and the Pontic Arc was of Indo-European origin, closely related to the Balto-Slavic languages (with elements of the Thracian-Dacian tradition), and that this substrate was overlaid by the steppe languages of the broadly defined Indo-Iranian circle, then the emergence of such a koine-type contact language becomes a likely result of prolonged contact. Such a scenario fits well with Florin Curta’s ‘Slavic lingua franca’ model and with the approach of Lindstedt and Salmela, who view the Proto-Slavic idiom as having been shaped under conditions of intense contact and migration in the Danube-Pontic zone. I emphasise that this is not a claim of identity between “*Limigantes* = *Antes* = Slavs”, but a proposal to view the name *Limigantes* as an earlier stage of the same type of borderland formation which, two centuries later, we know as the *Antes* within the Slavic linguistic horizon. This solution allows us to shift the chronology of the Slavic-speaking population’s participation in borderland structures further back without positing a single, sudden demographic ‘explosion’ in the 6th century; however, it remains a deliberately formulated authorial hypothesis requiring further research into the source material and the relationships between status names and ethnonyms in late antiquity.²⁰

6.4. The Bayesian heuristic approach and the principle of parsimony

From the perspective of historical methodology, the model presented here can also be evaluated using a Bayesian heuristic approach. This does not involve a strict numerical model with fully calibrated priors and likelihoods, as the source material is uneven and some of the premises are

²⁰ Jerome, *Chronicon* ad a. 334; Ammianus Marcellinus, *Res Gestae* XVII.12.9-10; Heather, *Empires and Barbarians*; Kardaras, *The Antes*; Curta, *The Making of the Slavs*; Curta, “The Slavic Lingua Franca”; Curta, *Slavs in the Making*; Lindstedt and Salmela; Slechta.

interdependent. Rather, it is a matter of formalising the intuition that when comparing two hypotheses — H0: the traditional chronology, in which the Slavs appear as a distinct force only around the year 500, and H1: the earlier presence of a Slavic-speaking population in borderland formations as early as the 4th century — the latter requires fewer additional, independent assumptions. In this sense, Bayesian heuristics and the principle of parsimony lead to a similar result: model H is cognitively ‘cheaper’ than H0, because rather than multiplying separate explanations for successive phenomena, it treats them as consequences of a single long-term process of koineisation in the borderlands. Under H0, one must simultaneously assume the late, approximately 500-year-old appearance of the Slavs in the sources, their exceptionally rapid spread across a vast area, their lack of earlier presence in borderland systems, and an independent explanation for a series of phenomena preceding the mid-6th century: the world of the Limigantes and Sarmatae servi in the 4th century, the attested 5th-century vocabulary of the *strava* and medos type within the Hun environment, dietary markers associated with millet, and the subsequent full visibility of the Antes and Sclaveni as a single linguistic world. In other words, H must interpret these data as a set of partially independent cases: the Limigantes’ rebellion separately, the Slavic-sounding vocabulary in Priscus and Jordanes separately, and the rapid success of the Slavic language separately. Under H1, however, the same classes of data form a sequence of a single process: the dependent and borderland layer already existed in the 4th century; in the 5th century, its idiom became audible in the ritual and table lexicon of Attila’s world; and in the 6th century, the koine reached the level of full source visibility. This does not, of course, mean that a mathematically precise posterior probability has been obtained here in the sense of formal historical statistics. It does, however, mean that, after combining the source, philological, lexical, archaeobotanical and sociolinguistic data, the likelihood ratio $P(E|H1) / P(E|H0)$ must be considered to be clearly greater than one. The application of the principle of parsimony therefore suggests that the hypothesis of an earlier presence of a Slavic-speaking population in the borderland systems is a model that is more coherent and less costly in terms of assumptions than the traditional picture of the ‘sudden’ appearance of the Slavs around the year 500. It is precisely in this strictly methodological form that the Bayesian argument reinforces the thesis of this study: that the Antes are best understood as a late-Antic, Slavic-speaking configuration of a long-standing borderland world, whose earlier phases remain identifiable under status and political names such as Limigantes.²¹

7. Conclusion and further research

7.1. Conclusion

The analysis conducted leads to the conclusion that the Antes are best understood as a borderland ethnonym, rather than a simple name for a single ‘people’ in a biological or ethnic sense. The community described by 6th-century sources already functions within the Slavic linguistic horizon, but the name itself may retain an older, Sarmatian-Iranian semantic layer associated with the frontier, guarding and border control, firmly rooted in the Indo-Iranian field of *anta* – *pāla/pālaka* – *argalā*. This does not yet constitute proof of a single, linear ethnic continuity from the Sarmatians to the early Slavs. It does, however, mean that in the late antique world, political and regional names could survive a change of language and the reorganisation of communities, provided they retained their value as designations of specific borderland zones and functions. In this sense, the case of the Antes has broader significance than the history of a single ethnonym. It demonstrates how various layers of linguistic heritage might have interacted in the Pontic-Carpathian borderland: older

²¹ “Bayesian” is used here heuristically rather than as a fully quantified statistical model with calibrated priors and likelihoods.

Sarmatian-Iranian vocabulary, a local Baltic-Slavic substrate (with elements of the Thracian-Dacian tradition), and later Slavic communicative practice. The Antes thus become not so much a mystery of ‘the origin of a single people’ as a case study of the long-lasting nature of a political and border name in a world where languages and power structures are subject to change, yet some borderland terms retain their functional continuity. The aim of this study was to demonstrate that the term ‘Antes’ can—albeit only circumstantially—be dated back to the year 334, when sources record a rebellion by the Limigantes as a dependent group (Sarmatae servi) along the middle Danube. A comparison of the accounts by Jerome and Ammianus on the Limigantes with the later appearance of the Antes in Jordanes and Procopius along the same broadly defined Danube- Pontic axis allows us to propose a hypothesis of functional continuity between these names: the Limigantes as an earlier borderland formation, the Antes as a later, ‘elevated’ ethnonym of the same zone under the dominance of the Slavic koine. Such an interpretation allows for a downward shift in the chronology of the participation of the Slavic-speaking population in borderland systems, without postulating a single, sudden demographic ‘explosion’ only in the 6th century. The second objective was to use lexical and dietary evidence from the Huns’ environment – primarily the forms *strava*, *medos/medas* and *millet* – as indications of the presence of a Slavic-influenced koine within the Hunnic Empire as early as the mid-5th century. In light of Maenchen-Helfen’s analyses, who linked *strava* to the mediation of a Slavic informant, and the latest biomolecular research by Macháček et al. on the diet of the early Slavs in Bohemia and Moravia (a strong reliance on millet processing, a higher proportion of milk and honey), such an interpretation is consistent with the principle of parsimony. Rather than viewing these forms as a collection of random similarities, this study proposes treating them as traces of a Slavic borderland koine, already present in the Hunnic-Sarmatian milieu prior to the ‘official’ appearance of the Sclaveni and the Antes in Byzantine sources. The third step was to outline a scenario in which the rapid and widespread dissemination of a relatively uniform Slavic language across Central Europe and the Balkans does not require the assumption of a sudden demographic ‘boom’, but can be explained as the result of the earlier formation of a koine in the borderlands between the Baltic- Slavic substrate and the steppe languages of the Iranian circle. In such a model, the linguistic substrate of the Carpathian-Pontic zone would have an Indo-European character close to the Balto-Slavic languages, with the participation of the Thracian-Dacian tradition, overlaid by successive layers of Sarmatian-Iranian influences; it was only against this backdrop, in the 4th–6th centuries, that the Slavic koine developed as a supra-tribal communicative idiom within the structures of the borderlands. Such a scenario aligns well with Florin Curta’s concept of a Slavic lingua franca and with the approach of Lindstedt and Salmela, who view Proto-Slavic as the result of prolonged contact and a language shift in the Danube-Pontic zone. Finally, this work had a methodological ambition: to demonstrate that ethnonyms of late antiquity — such as the Antes — can be studied simultaneously as names of historical communities, as forms rooted in specific semantic fields, and as elements of the long-term language of borderland politics. In this sense, the ‘evidence’ is multi-layered: it brings together historical accounts (Limigantes, Antes), philological analyses (the model *anta* – *pāla/pālaka* – *argalā*) and new biomolecular and isotopic data to construct a coherent, though deliberately non-definitive, model of the presence and role of the Slavic-speaking population in the borderland formations of the 4th–6th centuries. The final, scientifically sound conclusion is therefore: the Antes are a Slavic-speaking borderland community, whose name may retain an older, Sarmatian-Iranian

semantic layer, and their case allows us to re-date and reinterpret the process of Slavic koineisation in Central and Eastern Europe.²²

7.2. Further directions for research

The present study was conceived as a case study designed to examine whether the term ‘Antes’ can meaningfully be pushed back in time towards the year 334, when sources attest to a Limigant revolt along the middle Danube, and whether circumstantial evidence can indicate the presence of a Slavic-influenced koine in the Huns’ vicinity as early as the mid-5th century. More broadly, the aim was to ascertain whether the ‘sudden’ appearance of the Slavs in the sources around the year 500 must be interpreted as the beginning of the actual presence of a Slavic-speaking population in the borderland systems, or whether it can rather be understood as a change in the category of description and nomenclature. The results are promising, but they require further development and verification across several parallel lines of research. Firstly, it seems essential to carry out a systematic comparison of all known accounts concerning the Limigantes, Argaragantes and Antes in terms of ‘borderland names’ – taking into account not only the writings of Jerome, Ammianus, Jordanes, Procopius and Menander, but also lesser-known passages from the late antique Latin and Greek traditions. The aim of such a project would be to describe precisely the contexts in which these names appear, the social and military functions associated with them, and whether it is possible to identify a functional continuity between the Limigantes and the Antes without resorting to a simple ethnic identification. This would allow us to verify the hypothesis that the Limigantes represent an earlier stage of the same type of borderland formation which, two centuries later, we know as the Antes within the Slavic linguistic sphere. Secondly, further research is needed into the lexical traces of the Slavic koine in sources concerning the Hunnic and post-Hunnic empires. The interpretation presented here of the forms *strava*, *medos/medas* and millet as elements of a Slavic-influenced contact idiom is based on Maenchen-Helfen’s analyses and on the latest results of biomolecular research into the diet of the early Slavs in Central Europe. However, it requires expansion to include a systematic analysis of the entire corpus of culinary, ritual and table-related terms in the tradition of Priscus, Jordanes and other 5th–6th-century authors, cross-referenced with archaeobotanical and isotopic data from various regions of the Danube-Pontic arc. Only such an interdisciplinary approach will allow us to determine whether the observed similarities are indeed traces of a Slavic koine, or whether they fall within the broader repertoire of Indo-European dietary practices. Thirdly, the hypothesis of the rapid spread of a relatively uniform Slavic language as a borderland koine requires further integration with genetic and archaeological research. Recent aDNA analyses from the Avar cemeteries at Mödling and Leobersdorf show that populations of distinctly different origins can coexist within a single political order, maintaining reproductive barriers for several generations whilst exhibiting almost identical burial customs. This finding supports a general model in which political designations, koine languages and actual biological diversity do not simply overlap. However, genetic and archaeological research focusing directly on the areas associated with the Limigantes and the Antes is needed to determine whether similar structures of multi-ethnic borderland formations, as seen in the Avar world, can be observed in these regions. Fourthly, it is worth developing the linguistic dimension of the model proposed here, by linking the reconstruction of the semantic field of *anta* – *pāla/pālaka* – *argalā* with the more general concepts of migration and language shift in research on the spread of the Slavic languages. Approaches such as Florin Curta’s ‘Slavic lingua franca’ or the model by Lindstedt and Salmela, which emphasise the role of rapid migration, language change and regional variation, provide a

²² Curta, *The Making of the Slavs*; Curta, “The Slavic Lingua Franca”; Kardaras, “Sclaveni and Antes”; Lindstedt and Salmela.

natural framework for further studies into how specific borderland terms were adopted, translated and reinterpreted within the developing Slavic koine. A particularly promising area here appears to be the systematic analysis of Slavic-Iranian lexical relations in the semantics of the border, guard and authority, taking into account more recent studies on Iranian loanwords in Proto-Slavic. Finally, the question of a more formal formulation of the Bayesian heuristics used in this study remains open. A preliminary, qualitative application of the principle of parsimony suggests that a model of the earlier presence of a Slavic-speaking population in the borderland formations of the 4th–5th centuries better integrates the available textual, philological, lexical and archaeobotanical data than the traditional picture of the sudden appearance of the Slavs around the year 500. Future research could attempt to translate this intuition into more formalised models, taking into account various dating scenarios, different weights assigned to particular types of sources, and new data from archaeology, genetics and historical linguistics. Only such a multi-faceted approach will ultimately allow us to assess to what extent the Antes and Limigantes can be regarded as successive phases of a single, multi-ethnic borderland formation within which the Slavic koine of the early Middle Ages took shape.

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